

Factors Influencing Smallholder Farmers' Participation in Tomato Production in Ondo State, Nigeria

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18172628>

Abstract

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicon*) is widely cultivated for its significant economic, nutritional, and health benefits. The study identified the factors influencing smallholder farmers' participation in tomato production in Akure-North and Akure-South Local Government Areas, Ondo State, Nigeria. The study specifically determined the attitudes of the farmers towards tomato production, the factors that influenced farmers' participation in its production and the constraints faced by the farmers during tomato production. The study data were collected through the administration of well-structured questionnaire to respondents selected through a multi-stage sampling technique and data were analyzed using percentages and mean scores. The study revealed that there were more males (58.1%) in tomato production and majority (48.3%) of the respondents were between 31-40 years. Most respondents (43.0%) used both family and hired labour; more than half (52.0%) of the respondents had no access to extension services and mean tomato farm size was 1.23 hectares. The study further revealed that food security ($\bar{x}=3.36$) and access to market information ($\bar{x}=3.17$) were the most influencing factor in tomato production while pest and diseases infestation was the major constraint ($\bar{x}=3.37$). The hypothesis tested revealed a significant relationship between the attitude of the respondents to tomato production and factors influencing tomato production such as availability of quality seeds and income generation. The study recommends that the government and relevant stakeholders should improve on the structure of extension services so as to enhance dissemination of relevant information, and facilitate farmers' access to credit facilities and improved seedlings.

Keywords: *Smallholder Farmers, Tomato Production, Food Security, Market Information, and Extension Service*

INTRODUCTION

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicon*) is a fruit from the nightshade family native to South America widely cultivated for its significant economic, nutritional, and health benefits (Swamy, 2023). Tomatoes are rich in vitamin A and C, potassium and lycopene, a powerful antioxidant that has been linked to a reduced risk of cancer and heart disease (Balali *et al.*, 2025). Tomato farming has expanded significantly as a result of the crop's rise in popularity over the past 50 years. Nigeria's annual tomato imports are valued at 170 million with import volume of 150,000 tonnes (Sahel, 2024). This is because tomato is highly consumed across all the regions of the country, constituting about 18% of the daily vegetable consumption of households. Small-holder farmers in Nigeria have shown increasing interest in tomato production due to

its high demand and potential for profitability. The average farm size for small scale tomato farmers in South West zone of Nigeria is about 0.63 hectares (Ogundeji and Ogunwande, 2024). However, the cultivation of the crop remains a major challenge for small holder farmers in Nigeria. According to Oladoyin (2024), lack of access to finance is a significant barrier to small-holder farmers' participation in tomato production. The author further found that the high cost of inputs, such as seeds, fertilizers, and pesticides, is another major challenge for small-holder farmers in tomato cultivation. Other significant constraints identified by the author is lack access to information on best practices for tomato production, which affects their productivity and profitability. It reveals that only 30% of small-holder farmers have access to extension services, which provides them with the necessary information and technology for tomato production.

Therefore, this study investigated factors influencing farmers' participation in tomato production in Akure North and Akure South Local Government Area, Ondo State. Hence, this study was carried out to achieve the following specific objectives:

- i. ascertain the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents in the study area;
- ii. examine the factors influencing tomato production among the respondents;
- iii. determine the attitudes of the respondents towards tomato production; and
- iv. identify the constraints faced by the farmers in tomato production.

The hypothesis tested in the study is as follows:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the attitudes of the respondents towards tomato production and the factors influencing tomato production among the respondents.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Ondo State, Nigeria. Tomato farmers in the State constituted the study population. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to select respondents for the study. Akure-North and Akure-South Local Government Areas (LGAs) were purposively selected out of the 18 Local Government Areas (LGAs) because of their notable involvement in tomato production in the State. Secondly, three (3) communities were randomly selected from Akure-South LGA while two (2) communities in Akure-North LGA. Thereafter, twenty (25) respondents who are small scale farmers involved tomato production were purposively selected using snowballing technique from each of the communities to arrive at 125 respondents for the study. Primary data obtained with the aid of well-structured questionnaire directly administered to the respondents were used for the study. Information on socio-economic characteristics were obtained directly from the respondents. Perceived factors influencing tomato production, the attitudes of the respondents towards tomato production, and the constraints in tomato production were operationalized on a 5-point Likert scale response of strongly agreed, Agreed, Undecided, Disagree and Strongly disagree scored as 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively to several statements. The score summed up to 15 and was divided by 5 to obtain a mean score of 3 for the each of the statement. Mean scores below 3 were regarded as low and those above were regarded as high, the mean was for tabulated and presented for each statement. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and means statistics were used for data analysis while the Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test the hypothesis for the study. A sum was obtained to arrive at attitude score and another for factors influencing score. The two scores were correlated using PPMC to determine relationship between attitudes of the respondents towards tomato production and the factors influencing tomato production.

RESULTS

Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Respondents.

Majority (58.1%) of the respondents were male and most of the tomato farmers were between 31-40 years old with a mean age of 38.7 years. The results reflect that though the farmers were male dominated, tomato production gives opportunity for females participation, and the fact that majority were young, implies the farmers were capable of providing the needed manpower in tomato production. Only about 7.4% of the respondents were not educated and about 33.1% of the respondents had tertiary education ranging from OND to post graduate. This implies that education is no barrier to being a tomato farmer. The average farm size was 1.23 hectares with 38.6% of the respondents cultivating between 1.1 to 2.5 hectares implying the respondents operated on a small scale. Furthermore, majority (68.7%) of the respondents use both family and hired labour for tomato production, while about half (49.8%) of the respondents used only self/family labour. This shows that farmers can cope with the labour demand for tomato production. The study revealed a low access to extension services with only 23.7% of the respondents having access to extensive services throughout the cycle of tomato production. Amar (2023), affirmed that 73.3% of tomato farmers in South Odisha were small scale holders cultivating about 0.5 acres and they were mostly youths between 33 to 50 years.

Table 1: Respondents' Socio-Economic Characteristics

Characteristics	Percentage	Mean
Gender		
Male	58.1	
Female	41.9	
Farmers' Age (Years)		
≤ 30	16.1	
31 – 40	48.3	38.7±3.13
41 – 50	24.2	
> 50	11.4	
Level of education		
No formal education	7.4	
Primary education	18.9	
Secondary education	40.6	
Tertiary education	33.1	
Farm size (hectares)		
≤ 1	35.2	
1.1 – 2.5	38.6	1.03±0.78
2.6 – 4.0	26.2	
Type of labour used		
Self/Family	*49.8	
Hired	*24.2	
Both hired and family	*68.7	
Communal	*6.9	
Access to Extension Services	23.7	

Source: Field Survey, 2023. * Multiple responses

Perceived Factors Influencing Tomato Production

Table 2 showed the perceived factors influencing tomato production in descending order. The provision of food and necessary vitamins for the family ranked the most significant factor with has the highest mean score of (\bar{x} =3.33), availability of quality seeds (\bar{x} =3.11), availability of affordable fertilizers and other chemical inputs (\bar{x} =3.09), availability of affordable labour (\bar{x} =3.02), accessibility to credit facilities and the use of pesticides (\bar{x} =2.95), adequate water supply (\bar{x} =2.93), the availability of market for tomato (\bar{x} =2.87), government policies and incentives (\bar{x} =2.85), with the least factor influencing tomato production to be soil type (\bar{x} =2.40).

All the factors below the mean score of 3 were regarded as not important factors while those above 3 were regarded as important factors influencing tomato production. Hence, from the study, provision of food and nutrition, availability of quality seeds, fertilizer and chemical inputs, affordable labour and means of income generation were the important factors that influenced farmers' involvement in tomato production. Oladoyin (2024) ascertained that farm size and availability of farm inputs influenced tomato production.

Table 2: Perceived Factors Influencing Tomato Production among the Respondents

Factors	Mean
Provision of means of food and necessary vitamins for the family	3.33
Availability of quality seeds affects tomato production.	3.11
Availability of affordable fertilizers and other chemical inputs.	3.09
Availability of affordable labour	3.02
Capable of providing means of income generation	3.10
Accessibility of credit facilities	2.95
Availability of pesticides	2.95
Adequate water supply	2.93
Guaranteed market.	2.87
Government policies and incentives influences tomato production positively	2.85
The distance from the farm to the market affects tomato production.	2.81
The quality of transportation affects tomato production.	2.77
The availability of farming equipment affects tomato production.	2.73
The seasonality and cycles of tomato cultivation	2.67
The availability of extension services	2.55
The availability of simple technologies	2.42
The soil type affects tomato production.	2.40

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Attitude of the Respondents towards Tomato Production

Table 3 shows the attitude of the respondents towards tomato production. It shows that the respondents practiced tomato production mainly because it is important to food security (\bar{x} =3.36), closely followed by it is a sustainable agricultural practice (\bar{x} =3.26), it can provide funds to meet urgent family needs (\bar{x} =3.18), its potential to improve livelihood (\bar{x} =3.14), and the last which is physical work and the challenges associated with tomato farming are bearable

(\bar{x} =3.36). It can be implied from the study that the farmers have favourable attitudes towards tomato production as all the statements have scores above the cutoff point of 3.

Table 3: Attitude of Respondents towards tomato production

Statements	Mean
I got involved in tomato farming because it is important for food security.	3.36
I cultivate tomato because of the sustainable agricultural practices involved	3.22
I got involved in tomato production because of it can provide funds to meet urgent family needs	3.18
I got involved in tomato farming because it has the potential to improve livelihood.	3.14
I cultivate tomato because of its short cycle of production and maturity	3.04
I got involved in tomato farming because it does not require much finances	3.02
I got involved in tomato farming because it is culturally friendly.	3.01
I got involved in tomato farming because its farm can be located close to place of living	3.01
Physical work and the challenges associated with tomato farming are bearable	3.00

Source: Field survey, 2023

The Constraints Encountered by the Farmers in Tomato Production

Table 4 highlights the constraints faced by the farmers in tomato production. Pest and diseases infestation was the major challenge (\bar{x} =3.39), followed by high cost of transportation and inadequate logistics support resulting in a huge loss due to high perishability of tomato (\bar{x} =3.37), limited access to timely and affordable credit, limited and inadequate infrastructure (\bar{x} =3.36), limited access to storage and preservation facilities (\bar{x} =3.35), limited support and technical assistance (\bar{x} =3.32), limited access to affordable labour and skilled workforce (\bar{x} =3.29), difficulty in accessing reliable market channels (\bar{x} =3.28), lack of government policies and support (\bar{x} =3.25), climate change and unpredictable weather (\bar{x} =3.17), limited access to quality seeds (\bar{x} =3.14) with the least challenges faced by the respondents during tomato production which is the lack of access to information of market demands (\bar{x} =2.97). The results reinforce the need for improvement in tomato production technologies that could tackle pest and diseases, the high perishability of tomato and storage techniques among others. The results in this study is corroborated by Oladoyin (2024) who identified challenges identified in tomato production as unfavorable climate, theft, price instability, poor seed supply, and inadequate capital.

Table 4: The Challenges Faced by the Farmers during Tomato Production

Challenges	Mean
Pest and disease infestation.	3.39
High cost of transportation and logistics.	3.37
Inadequate infrastructure, such as poor roads.	3.36
Limited access to timely and affordable credit limits.	3.36
Limited access to storage and preservation facilities.	3.35

Limited support and technical assistance.	3.32
Limited access to affordable labour and skilled workforce.	3.29
Difficulty in accessing reliable market channels.	3.28
Lack of government policies and support to promote tomato production.	3.25
Climate change and unpredictable weather patterns.	3.17
Limited access to quality seeds.	3.14
Poor post-harvest handling practices.	3.08
High costs of inputs.	3.02
Limited access to finance and credit facilities.	2.98
Thefts	2.97

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Relationship between the attitude of the respondents to tomato production and factors influencing tomato production.

H₀₁: There's no significant relationship between the attitude of the respondents towards tomato production and the factors influencing tomato production among the respondents. The null hypothesis was rejected as the result ($r = 0.26$, $p = 0.03$) shown on Table 5 revealed a significant relationship between the two variables.

Table 5: Correlation Analysis showing relationship between the attitude of the respondents to tomato production and factors influencing tomato production

Relationship	r-value	Df	p-value	Decision
Attitude versus factors influencing tomato production	0.26	71	0.03*	Significant.

Source: Field survey, 2023. *Significant at 0.05 level.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Men and youths were more involved in tomato production. Provision of food and necessary vitamins; availability of quality seeds; affordable fertilizers and other chemical inputs; availability and affordable labour; adequate water supply; availability of market for tomato were the major factors that influenced tomato production. The study established that farmers have favourable attitude to tomato production. The major constraints encountered in tomato production were; pest and diseases infestation; limited access to timely and affordable credit; limited and inadequate infrastructure; and limited access to storage and preservation facilities. The favorable attitude towards tomato production creates opportunities for scaling tomato production through targeted support.

The study recommends the need for improvement in tomato production technologies that could tackle pest and diseases, the high perishability of tomato, storage techniques and similar barriers to tomato production. The Government and other stakeholders especially the private extension agencies should improve on extension services for enhanced and timely information delivery, facilitation of access to credit, market and necessary inputs.

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